

D 4.2

Different methods of stakeholders' engagement

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D 4.2	Different methods of stakeholders' engagement
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Partners short names

ENVI	Parco Scientifico Tecnologico Per L'ambiente Environment Park Torino Spa
IMI	Institute For Methods Innovation
IME	Fundacion IMDEA Energia
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
CNH2	Centro Nacional Del Hidrogeno
RIGP	Regionalna Izba Gospodarcza Pomorza
CLUSTER TWEED	Cluster Tweed
BH2C	Balkanski Vodoroden Klaster

Abbreviations

HRS	Hydrogen Refuelling Stations
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Executive Summary

HYPOP project aims to raise public awareness and trust towards hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits. To do this, **stakeholders' engagement** is a pivotal aspect, and the project developed and implemented a number of **co-creation workshops** to include the project's target groups in the development of guidelines supporting the institutional and technical stakeholders in the safety, permitting and certification of hydrogen technologies.

Overall, HyPOP organised:

- One international awareness raising workshop during the 2024 Hydrogen Week (November 2024)
- Some local workshops and meetings in Spain, Bulgaria and Italy, during a preliminary phase of engagement (2024); these three workshops were preparatory with respect to the "official" stakeholders' engagement workshops;
- Five local stakeholders' engagement workshops, one each in Spain, Bulgaria, Poland, Italy and Belgium, all following a common format.

The workshops followed a common structure and a portfolio of questions that were used to engage the public and the speakers and obtain useful inputs in the finalisation of the guidelines on permitting, safety and certification, which are some of the final outcomes of the project.

In pursuing its objectives of gathering information about procedures on safety, permitting and certification and of creating guidelines on the same topics, HyPOP project created a wide range of opportunities for meeting stakeholders and favouring interactions and open discussions. **In person meetings in the local language of the stakeholders were held to facilitate the exchange of experiences and also to understand at best the good practices and the gaps in the HyPOP countries.**

Many stakeholders from the industry and industry associations, research organisations, certification bodies and business support organisation took part in the initiative. Industry associations were key in supporting the engagement of speakers and audiences. Owing to their intervention, in some Countries local permitting and safety authorities also took part in the panels, but there was some resistance in other locations despite invitations being sent to direct contacts.

The results of the discussions have been used to inform the development of the guidelines on safety, permitting and certification, which are publicly available on the HyPOP website.

1 Introduction

HYPOP project aims to raise public awareness and trust towards hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits. To do this, stakeholders' engagement is a pivotal aspect, and the project developed and implemented a number of co-creation workshops to include the project's target groups in the development of guidelines supporting communication of hydrogen towards the public (D3.4 "Guidelines for public engagement on H2 technologies' implementation") and Guidelines supporting the institutional and technical stakeholders in the safety, permitting and certification of hydrogen technologies (Deliverables 4.3 to 4.5).

This report provides information on the meetings, awareness raising events and workshops targeting institutional stakeholders, summarising the main outcomes and lessons learned.

Overall, HyPOP organised:

- One international awareness raising workshop during the 2024 Hydrogen Week (November 2024)
- Some local workshops and meetings in Spain, Bulgaria and Italy, during a preliminary phase of engagement (2024); these three workshops were preparatory with respect to the "official" stakeholders' engagement workshops;
- Five local stakeholders' engagement workshops, one each in Spain, Bulgaria, Poland, Italy and Belgium, all following a common format.

The workshops aimed to engage permitting and (fire) safety authorities, first responders, adopters, hydrogen projects developers, certification bodies, to share experiences, highlight good practices and potential gaps in permitting and licensing approaches. Supporting materials for and reports of each workshop is presented in the Annexes.

2 Preliminary activity

A first series of workshops and meetings was held during the period June to November 2024. These included:

- An international awareness raising workshop held in Brussels during the 2024 Hydrogen Week
- Two local workshops held in Spain and Italy in October 2024
- A number of meetings with representatives of local institutions were held in Bulgaria in 2024.

These meetings resulted useful as a preparatory activity for the official stakeholders' workshops held in the HyPOP Countries during 2025. The 2024 meetings had mostly the objective of raising the awareness about the project and identifying potential stakeholders for the 2025 workshops. They were also used to test the format of the stakeholders' engagement workshops to be held later on, including the categories of speakers to be invited, the questions, the target audience and its engagement.

2.1 THE INTERNATIONAL AWARENESS RAISING WORKSHOP

HyPOP took part in the Hydrogen Week 2024 with a booth in the EU Projects Pavillon (see D5.8). It also organised a side event held on the morning of the 19th of November. The Agenda is available in section 5.

The objectives of the workshop were to:

- Implement an engagement activity: gathering new experiences and needs from the audience (engagement goal); establish a useful discussion among different types of involved stakeholders, to better understand different points of view, identify barriers, needs and put the basis for the final guidance documents (co-creation goal). Taking in consideration it is an international event, so procedures/regulations are discussed at general level among European/international representatives.
- Support the structuring of the guidelines: collection of data to create specific guidelines (in this case, technical) for the H2 implementation by using Best Practices from different case studies. Call to action to the audience for the best practices/experience collection.
- Explore specifically the mobility and residential European experiences, analysing certification, safety, and authorisation aspects. Specific topics:
 - HRS: stationary/mobile with on-site production; HRS stationary/mobile without on-site production;
 - Mobility: buses/trains;
 - Residential: domestic hydrogen boilers/generators; domestic hydrogen boilers/generators with storage; domestic hydrogen boilers/generators with on-site production with mains' gas.

Speakers invited introduced their work and discussed their experience in the key topics of safety, permitting and certification. Speakers represented:

- Funded projects that demonstrated hydrogen technologies in the mobility (MultHyFuel, H2PORTS and FCH2Rail) and residential sector (with a certification stakeholder (TUV Sud)

and residential/stationary sectors (DEMOSOFC, REMOTE, SUSTAINHUTS and EVERYWH2ERE)

- Certification bodies illustrated the available standards and regulatory references for the stationary/ residential and mobility sector.

A final panel was held on the experience of various stakeholders (Hydrogen Europe, Hydrogen Poland, RINA - the Italian certification body, a Finnish Foundation) in cooperating with local authorities, including firefighters.

The questions asked to the panels and to the public are reported in section 5.

The speakers presented successful cases of interaction with the public authorities, mostly due to a cooperative approach that involved authorities from the beginning. The importance of the reference standards - and the work currently being undertaken by the standardisation bodies- was also highlighted. The EU projects invited highlighted some differences in approaches amongst the Countries involved in the demonstrations and how barriers have been overcome (e.g., EVERYWH2ERE site that host the H2 electrolyser) due to an easier interaction with the fire safety authority, which for the demo in Spain was the local authority in charge of permitting also.

TAKE AWAYS: the innovation brought about by many projects also includes very useful approaches to the regulators and authorities in charge of permitting and licensing. This “soft” experimentation is to be taken into account in the Guidelines and should be further encouraged.

Figure 1 HyPOP project at the Hydrogen Week 2024, Bruxelles

2.2 PRELIMINARY WORKSHOPS IN SPAIN AND ITALY

2.2.1 CNH2 event- 10th of October 2024, CNH2 premises, PUERTOLLANO, SPAIN

The “HYPOP Project: Tackling barriers in the hydrogen sector” event was organised by partner CNH2 in cooperation with Tecniberia, the Spanish Association of Engineering, Consulting and Technology Services Companies. The companies highlighted the lack of a reference national regulation, but also that standards, where available, helped the permitting. However, many autonomous authorities had worked on guidelines to support the process – still, a unified regulation or standard would support the process for companies working in different parts of the Country. A few remarks were made on the misalignment between strategies on hydrogen and lack of specific permitting guidelines. Please see Section 6 for a full report.

TAKE AWAYS: A well-defined procedure is required to establish the characteristics needed and the requirements for permitting, safety and certification in order to develop green hydrogen projects. It also has to be uniform across all regions of Spain. The main authorities involved in granting permits are also suggested for identification.

Figure 2 The CNH2 event of the 10th of October 2024, Puertollano

2.2.2 FUELING TOMORROW EVENT – 10th of October 2024, BOLOGNA ITALY

HyPOP liaised with the Italian Hydrogen Association H2IT for organising a seminar during day 2 of the Bologna event “Fuelling Tomorrow”. The seminar focused on mobility applications and included the launch of the H2IT position paper on HRS. Through the Association, HyPOP was involved as speakers, representatives from a large hydrogen distributor (Linde), HRS developers (Edison Next) and a local transport authority introducing its hydrogen-fuelled bus fleet (TPER). The various stakeholders contributed to the discussion by sharing their experience in trying to implement HRS, hydrogen fleets and cryogenic hydrogen solutions. Representatives from the Fire Brigade Corp at National and local levels were invited but declined. Around 10 people were in the audience, and a recording of the seminar is available on YouTube¹. The agenda of the day is reported in section 7.

HyPOP project was presented, with specific focus on the findings of the analysis of the permitting and safety procedures. The discussion remarked that in Italy, there are no specific reference standards for hydrogen, so we are far behind in terms of regulations. At the same time, the government has earmarked the funding and construction of refuelling stations throughout Italy by

¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KoP3W2SfhFA>

2026, thanks to the Recovery Fund. Companies and organisations therefore face various regulatory barriers when installing the devices.

TAKE AWAYS: alignment between strategies and regulations is required. Involvement of local authorities, including safety permitting authorities, in the discussion is essential, however, their availability remains somewhat limited.

Figure 3 HyPOP project at Fuelling tomorrow, Bologna

2.3 MEETINGS in BULGARIA

The unofficial meetings held by BH2C during 2024 aimed to gather interest for the official local stakeholders' engagement workshop originally planned for the autumn of 2024 and moved to January 2025.

BH2C held an unofficial meeting with the Ministry of Transport of the Republic of Bulgaria in February 2024 regarding the current regulatory documents related to hydrogen and their effect on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria. The following operational goals were discussed:

- Encouraging the consistent and effective introduction of technologies for the production, transportation, and use of green hydrogen in industry, energy, and transport;

- Intensifying scientific research and innovation;
- Creating conditions for education and training for new professions and jobs, and for an informed consumer and administrative environment related to hydrogen technologies;
- Stimulating European and international cooperation.

The topic of installing charging stations to stimulate the development of various hydrogen-powered vehicles was also discussed. Practices and technologies for the transportation of hydrogen were also discussed. The HYPOP project was mentioned, and the Ministry of Transport was informed about the upcoming forum in the autumn, for which they would receive an official invitation.

In March 2024, BH2C held a meeting at the Bulgarian Chamber of Commerce and Industry. This is the second-largest business chamber in Bulgaria. BH2C acquainted its leadership in an unofficial meeting with the HYPOP project and the forum planned for the autumn of 2024 on the same project. Legislative and business practices were discussed to encourage the use of hydrogen.

BH2C held an informal meeting with the unions in April 2024 and informed their leadership about BH2C's participation in the HYPOP project. A number of important topics related to hydrogen were discussed, the main one being the planning, preparation, and implementation of a wide information campaign related to hydrogen as an energy source and widely accessible and mass seminars, courses, and other training for additional qualification and retraining of workers from various branches.

On May 10, 2024, BH2C was an official guest at the opening of the first Hydrogen Station in Bulgaria. The hydrogen charging station is the first part of the implementation of the project for the field laboratory "Integrated Energy Systems" of the Centre for Competence "Hitmobil" of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. The first hydrogen charging station marks the beginning of hydrogen-electric mobility in the country. The hydrogen charging station was manufactured by the Austrian company EDC-ANLAGENTECHNIK. It can charge cars at the two standard pressures for compressed hydrogen - 350 and 700 bar.

3 The stakeholders' engagement workshops

Within WP4, project HYPOP had committed to engage institutional stakeholders to feed the drafting of the guidelines to be issued at the end of the project. The preliminary activities informed the planning of the local workshops, which were held in 2025. They were held in the local language² in the HyPOP countries, i.e. Belgium, Bulgaria, Italy and Spain. **The choice of focusing on local languages had proved successful for the citizens engagement, and this was replicated in the stakeholders' engagement workshops.** Most of the workshops were held in person to stimulate networking alongside the event.

The workshops focused around application of hydrogen technologies in:

- Mobility: HRS- stationary/mobile with on-site production; HRS - stationary/mobile without on-site production;
- Residential/Stationary applications: domestic hydrogen boilers/generators; fuel cells for power and heat supply.

One or more panels of speakers were invited to present and discuss their experience and the way forward. If an audience was invited, it was given the opportunity to interact with live polls or questions.

National industry events had been chosen to gather the right audiences and to foster a dialogue between industry and institutions.

Objectives, targets, generic agenda and common questions are listed in the next section.

3.1 CALENDAR of EVENTS

Planning of the workshops started in October 2024, so as to secure slots in any hydrogen related events in the calendar of the partners or in the calendar of hydrogen events in the different HyPOP countries.

The events were held according to the following calendar:

- BELGIUM: 24th Jan 2025, Online ad hoc event – Focus: Permitting authorities HRS/Certification, regional guidelines
- BULGARIA: 27th Jan 2025, in person ad hoc event
- SPAIN: 6th Feb 2025, in person event during Congresso National of Hydrogen, Andalusia
- POLAND: 15th May 2025, in person ad hoc event
- ITALY: 23rd May 2025, in person event during the H2 EXPO, Piacenza

Summaries of the events are reported in sections 5 and following.

² Except for Belgium, where English was used so to involve stakeholders from both French speaking Wallonia and Flemish speaking Flanders.

3.2 OBJECTIVES; TARGETS; and AGENDA of the LOCAL WORKSHOPS:

OBJECTIVES:

- **DISSEMINATE:** introduce the project and the general findings; introduce the S-LCA; focus on the findings related to the Country, introduce local best practices or best practices related to local projects if available.
- **FURTHER THE KNOWLEDGE:** gather further evidence of best practices or barriers encountered.
- **ENGAGE:** stimulate a discussion among different stakeholders to understand different needs and build a dialogue amongst parties
- **COCREATE:** share the proposed format of the final guidance documents and gather suggestions and “nice to have”.

TARGET (SPEAKERS AND AUDIENCE)

Alongside the Consortium representative for the Country, local speakers might also be engaged.

- First responders/fire fighters
- Permitting authorities – environmental, safety and urban/building
- Certification bodies
- Representatives of demo projects, hydrogen valleys, etc
- Integrators of technologies/installers/adopters
- Other local players

GENERIC AGENDA:

1. Introduction of HYPOP and main findings (DISSEMINATE)
2. National information: on H2 strategy and implementation prospect, on permitting, safety, certification (DISSEMINATE)
3. Discussion on the findings/ collection of further evidence on barriers/ best practices (FURTHER THE KNOWLEDGE)
4. Best practices collected at EU level (DISSEMINATE)
5. Discussion on applicability of best practices (from EU), barriers, needs at local level (ENGAGE)
6. Discussion on guidelines (COCREATE)
7. Wrap up

3.3 PROPOSED COMMON QUESTIONS

3.3.1 Multiple choice questions

These questions were used to gather information from the stakeholders in a quick manner, also through live polls. Alternatives were inserted to cater for different audiences

SAFETY

1) What are the main challenges in demonstrating the safety of hydrogen plants?

- A. Lack of harmonised technical standards and reference scenarios for risk assessment.
- B. Difficulty in accessing or generating data on accidental releases and real-world incidents.
- C. Limited training and awareness of hydrogen-specific risks among local authorities.
- D. Excessive reliance on conventional fossil fuel benchmarks in safety evaluations.

2) How have challenges in the safety evaluation process of hydrogen technologies been addressed?

- A. Development of dedicated hydrogen safety codes (e.g., ISO/TR 15916, NFPA 2).
- B. Establishment of early dialogue mechanisms between project developers and permitting bodies.
- C. Use of digital twin simulations to demonstrate compliance and mitigation scenarios.
- D. Consolidation of hydrogen-related responsibilities under centralised technical authorities.

3) What are the key advantages and disadvantages of your regulatory framework in ensuring hydrogen safety?

- A. Clear procedures and roles support efficient approval (advantage); lack of flexibility for novel systems (disadvantage).
- B. Strong legacy in industrial gas safety (advantage); slow integration of hydrogen-specific updates (disadvantage).
- C. Well-established emergency response protocols (advantage); regional inconsistencies in applying national rules (disadvantage).
- D. High transparency with stakeholders (advantage); overlapping responsibilities among authorities (disadvantage).

4) What improvements would you propose to overcome regulatory barriers?

- A. Create a centralised hydrogen permitting authority with technical and administrative capacity.
- B. Promote mutual recognition of safety assessments across EU member states.
- C. Offer incentives for early engagement with safety regulators in the project design phase.
- D. Develop targeted training programs for public authorities on hydrogen-specific risks.

PERMITTING

1) What are the main challenges in obtaining or granting permits?

- A. Unclear classification of hydrogen projects within existing legislative frameworks.
- B. Lack of coordinated timelines between environmental and safety permits.
- C. Excessive documentation burden with redundant reporting obligations.
- D. Delays due to limited local expertise in hydrogen risk assessment.

2) How does environmental permitting for hydrogen compare to other energy techs?

- A. Hydrogen projects face more scrutiny due to novelty and public perception.
- B. Permitting times are often longer due to interdependencies with other infrastructure (pipelines, storage).
- C. In contrast, solar and wind benefit from streamlined procedures not yet adapted for hydrogen.
- D. Environmental concerns are similar, but hydrogen lacks clear Best Available Techniques (BAT) references.

3) What are the key safety concerns and related administrative hurdles during permitting?

- A. Explosion risk and leak management dominate safety reviews.
- B. Limited integration between environmental impact assessment (EIA) and safety documentation.
- C. Authorities may require conservative design margins due to lack of experience.
- D. Current regulations only partially address real-time monitoring or incident reporting protocols.

4) Have you experienced differences in permitting processes between regions or municipalities?

- A. Yes, some regions have established hydrogen one-stop-shops, others follow outdated general procedures.
- B. Yes, divergent interpretations of safety distances and buffer zones are common.
- C. No, the process is harmonised through national-level digital platforms.
- D. Differences exist and delay implementation; coordination mechanisms between regions should be enforced.

CERTIFICATION

1) Which technologies are most impacted by gaps in standards or certification?

- A. Hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) due to varying pressure and fuelling protocols.
- B. Electrolysers and storage systems, especially above certain capacity thresholds.
- C. Combined heat and power (CHP) units using hydrogen blends.
- D. Off-grid or residential systems where national standards are still under development.

2) Are you aware of any certification guidelines or protocols? Which are most useful?

- A. Yes, ISO 14687 and related PEM fuel cell standards provide essential criteria.
- B. EU-level certification of origin schemes helps with cross-border project alignment.
- C. Useful: H2-readiness labels; Weakness: lack of clarity on testing procedures.
- D. National guidelines exist but require alignment with EU Taxonomy and RED II principles.

3) For certification bodies: What gaps and challenges do you foresee?

- A. Need for harmonized testing procedures across certification laboratories.
- B. Difficulty in verifying dynamic performance under realistic operating conditions.
- C. Lack of comprehensive protocols for hybrid or sector-coupled hydrogen systems.
- D. Growing demand outpaces capacity of qualified evaluators and facilities.

3.3.2 Open questions

The following questions were to be used mostly for engaging the speakers in a discussion where they could present their experience and points of view.

SAFETY

- 1) What are the main challenges in demonstrating the safety of hydrogen plants, either as an entity interacting with authorities or as an authority evaluating these technologies?

Please share your experience in the industry, mobility, and/or residential sectors.

- 2) How have challenges in the safety evaluation process of hydrogen technologies been addressed, either by entities interacting with authorities or by authorities themselves? Please share your experience or relevant examples from your country or others.
- 3) What are the key advantages and disadvantages of your regulatory framework in ensuring the safety compliance of hydrogen plants, from the perspective of both stakeholders interacting with authorities and authorities evaluating these projects? Please explain.
- 4) What improvements would you propose to overcome regulatory barriers in your country, considering both the perspective of stakeholders engaging with authorities and that of the authorities themselves? Please elaborate.

PERMITTING

- 1) What are the main challenges you have encountered in obtaining or granting permits for hydrogen-related projects? Please describe your experience with environmental, safety, construction and/or administrative requirements and explain specific bottlenecks that you believe should be addressed.
- 2) How does the environmental permitting process for hydrogen projects compare to that for other energy technologies in your country? Are there unique challenges or advantages, and what improvements would you suggest?
- 3) What are the key safety concerns and the related administrative hurdles that arise during the permitting process for hydrogen technologies? How well do current regulations address these concerns? Do you believe there is room for improvement?
- 4) Have you experienced significant differences in permitting processes between regions or municipalities within your country? If so, how do these disparities affect project implementation? Additionally, what improvements would you propose to harmonize or streamline these processes?

CERTIFICATION

- 1) Which technologies are most impacted by gaps in the standards framework and/or certification processes? Please share your perspective as a stakeholder or certification body, specifying the practical challenges and the relevant sectors and applications.
- 2) Are you aware of any certification guidelines or protocols? If so, which elements do you find most useful, and what improvements would you suggest?
- 3) For certification bodies: In which direction are you currently working, and what gaps and challenges do you foresee in the near future regarding hydrogen technologies?

3.4 USE OF THE INFORMATION GATHERED

The information obtained from the workshop has been used in the development of the Safety, permitting and certification guidelines. Please see deliverables D4.3 to D4.5.

4 Conclusions

In pursuing its objectives of gathering information about procedures on safety, permitting and certification and of creating guidelines on the same topics, HyPOP project created a wide range of opportunities for meeting stakeholders and favouring interactions and open discussions. In person meetings in the local language of the stakeholders were held to facilitate the exchange of experiences and also to understand at best the good practices and the gaps in the HyPOP countries.

Many stakeholders from the industry and industry associations, research organisations, certification bodies and business support organisations took part in the initiative. Industry associations were key in supporting the engagement of speakers and audiences. Owing to their intervention, in some Countries local permitting and safety authorities also took part in the panels, but there was some resistance in other locations despite invitations being sent to direct contacts.

The results of the discussions have been used to inform the development of the guidelines on safety, permitting and certification, which are publicly available on the HyPOP website.

5 Annex 1: EU Hydrogen week workshop

5.1 AGENDA

Co-funded by
the European Union

HYPOP Project – H2WEEK WORKSHOP

“Hydrogen for mobility and residential applications: safety and permitting approaches around Europe”

19TH Nov, 2024 09:00 – 13:00, Room 1124

Agenda

Moderator: Ilaria Schiavi, Project Manager and HYPOP Project Coordinator

09:00 – 09:15 Welcome from Clean Hydrogen JU

Alberto J. Garcia Hombrados - Project Officer, Clean Hydrogen Partnership JU

09:15 – 09:30 HYPOP: project overview

Mattia Miglietta - Project Manager, Environment Park

09:30 - 10:15 H2 Mobility Installations: best practices & experiences around Europe

Dr. Joana Fonseca - Senior Analyst, Market Intelligence, Hydrogen Europe

Zaneta Klostowska - Expert of hydrogen market development, certification and permitting, TÜV SÜD

Cristina Ballester - Research Engineer at the Engineering Unit of the Spanish National Hydrogen Center , Centro Nacional del Hidrógeno

10:15 – 10:45 Technical focus on permitting, safety, certification requirements

Interviews to the H2 Mobility Speakers' Panel

10:45 – 11:00 Coffee break

11:00 -11:45 H2 Residential Installations: best practices & experiences around Europe

Pedro Casero Cabezón - Technical Area Manager, Aragon Hydrogen Foundation

Massimo Santarelli - Prof. PhD, Full Professor Department of energy, Politecnico di Torino

Stephen McPhail - Business Development Manager Hydrogen, KIWA

11:45 – 12:15 Technical focus on permitting, safety, certification requirements

Interviews to the H2 Residential Speakers' Panel

12:15 – 13:00 Cooperating with public and institutional stakeholders throughout Europe – Roundtable

Joana Fonseca - Senior Analyst, Market Intelligence, Hydrogen Europe

Tomoho Umeda - President of the Board of Directors Hydrogen Poland Association

Esa Eerola - Project Manager, Central Finland Mobility Foundation (Cefmof)

Mattia Miglietta - Project Manager, Environment Park

Antonio Lucci - Global Energy Transition Strategic Streams Director, RINA Consulting

The event will be an interactive workshop where audience will be involved by using slide for the Q&A

5.2 QUESTIONS USED DURING THE WORKSHOP

Panel 1

Multhfuel project

- The regulatory framework and safety perception are critical factors when considering a hydrogen refuelling station, and perhaps even more when hydrogen comes to be integrated with other fuels. Which elements of the (European and national) regulatory framework for safety most influence the development of multifuel stations (e.g., SEVESO directive, national regulations, etc)?
- Your project has focused on risk analysis and the use of software that can assess risk scenarios such as hydrogen leakage and its effects on the surrounding environment. Risk analysis is a tool that allows you to objectively assess and guarantee the safety of an installation. In your opinion, how can it complement a more prescriptive approach?

TUV Sud

- Different technological solutions for hydrogen mobility are needed to support the supply/demand ratio of the hydrogen market. In this respect, do you see more critical issues for permitting standard refuelling stations or containerised/compact stations? Should they be considered equally?
- Staying on the topic of compact stations. As these are a potentially useful solution for increasing the number of demonstration projects and the familiarity of authorities and citizens with hydrogen, how does the authorities' approach to safety differ from standard solutions, where more safety measures can be employed?
- What are the main critical issues you have experienced during the certification processes of hydrogen technologies included in refuelling stations and of the refuelling station as a whole, even in the case of compact configurations? And how do you think these could be overcome?

CNH2 (H2ports/FCH2rail)

- Compared to the other projects we have seen, in your case safety, permitting and certification aspects were addressed in two particular environments, such as ports and railways, where the competent authorities are used to operating in standardised contexts characterised by the use/application of international standards and codes.
In your opinion, has it been complex to get a performance approach accepted?
- Given the novelty of hydrogen applications in port and railway contexts, is the application of regulations, procedures, and industry guidelines an element that favours the relationship between authority and positive project development? Instead, are these an acceptable compromise from the designer's point of view?

Common questions for all:

- In your opinion, what are the elements that can favour a hydrogen refuelling station project in the field of safety, permitting and certification?

MENTIMETER 1

- How much is hydrogen on site production a factor influencing the perception by the authorities or the demands in terms of safety and permitting procedures? Does it have an impact? What kind? (e.g., on timing procedures, etc)
- Has the technical preparation of the project assessment authorities influenced the project? If yes, in what way (positive/negative/indifferent)? Is there cooperation? Are there delays due to differing interpretations?

Panel 2

KIWA

- What are the characteristic elements of the permitting procedures you have shown for installations in the Netherlands? how do these tie in with the permitting guidelines for residential hydrogen pilot projects?

Prof Santarelli

- Did the installation site and the interaction with grid operators influence the permitting procedures?

Common questions for all:

- In your experience and in relation to the projects you have described, how much do the presence of on-site production and/or the amount of hydrogen stored influence the perception of national/local authorities and thus the demands in terms of safety and permitting procedures? What kind of impact do they have?
- The residential sector has the least practical experience in terms of demonstration projects and often lacks the appropriate regulatory references. In your opinion, what is needed today to foster the implementation of hydrogen technologies in residential contexts?

MENTIMETER 2

Panel 3

Hydrogen Europe

- Both as an association and through your project, you have had to deal with different authorities operating in different countries. What are the main safety issues you have encountered when interacting with institutional authorities? In which cases is there more openness (e.g., installation in urban or suburban contexts) and in which is there more closure

(e.g., local/national authority relationship) in the interaction and discussion of hydrogen projects?

Rina

- Today, we have seen presentations and experiences of different certification bodies. A certification body is often caught in the middle between the designer who needs to get the project approved and the authorities responsible for assessing the safety and certification aspects. We would like Rina to bring us his experience in interacting with the authorities....

Hynfra

- We would like to know if, as a representative of a country on the EU13 countries list, you see a general progress in policies, safety and permitting regulations and thus in the perception towards hydrogen and its technologies?

Central Finland Mobility Foundation

- Finland is not a country that has been treated within HYPOP, but is, together with the frontrunner countries mentioned, a virtuous example of openness and commitment of institutions towards hydrogen technologies. We would like to know whether you have addressed or imagine addressing certain critical issues related to safety, permitting and/or certification aspects, or what are the main concerns of the institutions and citizens you represent.

5.3 Answers by the audience

6 Annex 2: “HYPOP Project: Tackling barriers in the hydrogen sector” CNH2 workshop

WORKSHOP TITLE	HYPOP Project: Tackling barriers in the hydrogen sector
EVENT DATE	10 th October, 2024
DURATION	09:00 – 13:00
PLACE	CNH2 Premises
CO-ORGANISER (IF ANY)	TECNIBERIA (Spanish Association of Engineering, Consulting and Technology Services Companies)
SHORT DESCRIPTION (EACH SESSION, TYPE OF INTERACTION, TOPICS DISCUSSED)	<p>Different companies dedicated to engineering and energy renewable resources visited the CNH2 premises. In this case, it was a presential meeting where CNH2 explained the objectives of HYPOP project and the results obtained so far while some interactive were interspersed with the presentation. Then, companies and organizers discussed about what barriers they use to find when they work with hydrogen projects, such as regulatory barriers.</p> <p>The companies referred the barriers with the procedures for carrying out the projects. So, the main barrier was the lack of a specific national regulation in the hydrogen value chain. As a consequence, the different companies and authorities involved had to refer to similar yet-existing regulation: gaseous fuels storage, fuels distribution, natural-gas legislation, pressure equipment regulation, etc. In one case (HRS project), the permitting procedure was carried out applying the ISO strictly, showing no problems. In other cases, authorities and citizens were not so supportive.</p> <p>Other topics arisen were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While there is no national legislation, autonomous communities are taking steps at regional level (Andalucía guidelines, AeH2 report). • Importance of the firefighters in the commissioning of installations. They try to be up to date, but if there is no legislation it is difficult. • It is important to unify the regional criteria, e.g., through a common UNE standard. • Paradox between the PNIEC objectives and the lack of normative. • Paradox between the production of H₂ and the lack of off-takers. • Price of green H₂ and willingness to pay for it.

<p>SPEAKERS (NAME, AFFILIATION)</p>	<p>Gema María Rodado Nieto, Head of Consultancy and Training Unit of the Spanish National Hydrogen Centre (CNH2)</p> <p>María Panadero Camacho, Consultancy and Training Unit of the Spanish National Hydrogen Centre (CNH2)</p>
<p>INTERACTIVE QUESTIONS TO THE AUDIENCE (IF ANY)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In what part of the hydrogen value chain do you work? 2. In which part of a hydrogen project have you been most involved? 3. Think about national projects you know... Could you say which are the authorities to grant the implementation of this project? 4. With you experience, what is the part with more risks? 5. What is your experience in the process of hydrogen technologies certification? (Directly or indirectly) <p>According to your experience, What barriers have you found during the hydrogen technologies installation?</p>
<p>NR OF ATTENDANCE</p>	<p>6. 24</p>
<p>GENERAL INFO ABOUT THE AUDIENCE TYPE (e.g. x % of academia, x% of companies etc)</p>	<p>All the audience is from companies dedicated to engineering and renewable energies sectors, such as companies named below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Técnicas reunidas - Applus - Acciona energía - OCA Global - WSP - SOCOTEC - Ayesa - ARUP - VICTAULIC - FHECOR - EMPRESARIOS AGRUPADOS - MAI GROUP - GPYO - AECOM <p>7. TECNIBERIA</p>

Event agenda

- 10:00 am Welcome and reception of attendees
- 10:20 am Presentation of CNH2 and Tecniberia
- 10:40 am Introduction to HYPOP Project
 - Project presentation and main results to date
 - Interaction with participants (discussion and feedback)
- 11:40 am Visit to CNH2 facilities and laboratories
- 14:00 pm workshop ends

Interactive questions carried out during the presentation (slido):

1. ¿En qué parte de la cadena de valor del H2 trabaja?

Multiple Choice Poll 16 votes 16 participants

slido

2. ¿En qué fase de un proyecto de H2 se ha visto más involucrado? (Proyectos nacionales)

Multiple Choice Poll 16 votes 16 participants

slido

3. Piensa en los proyectos de hidrógeno nacionales que conoces... ¿Sabrías decir cuáles son las autoridades pertinentes para conceder la implantación/PEM de este proyecto?

Open text poll 15 responses 14 participants

- Anonymous
Industria comunidad autónoma Medioambiente Urbanismo de la comunidad autónoma y Ayto
- Anonymous
Bomberos
- Anonymous
Industria/ Comunidad autónoma/Ayto
- Anonymous
Administración regional
- Anonymous
Ministerio de Industria Autoridad competente de la comunidad donde se instala Ayuntamiento
- Anonymous
Ministerio de Industria Comunidad Autónoma
- Anonymous
administracion local y regional
- Anonymous
- Dirección General de Industria - Ayuntamientos - Consejería de Medio Ambiente
- Anonymous
Delegación provincial de industria
- Anonymous
ayuntamiento, servicios provinciales de industria
- Anonymous
Medio Ambiente Ayuntamientos ST Industria
- Anonymous
Ministerio de Industria
- Anonymous
NA
- Anonymous
Junta de la comunidad
- Anonymous
Industria, Medio ambiente

4. Según tu experiencia, ¿qué fase concentra más riesgos?

Multiple Choice Poll 13 votes 13 participants

slido

5. ¿Cuál es tu experiencia en el proceso de certificación de tecnologías del H2?
(directa o indirecta)

Open text poll 9 responses 9 participants

- Anonymous
Vacío regulatorio en purgas
- Anonymous
Certificación como ingeniería
- Anonymous
Certificación como Organismo Notificado y de Inspección
- Anonymous
no he participado
- Anonymous
N/A
- Anonymous
Sin experiencia.
- Anonymous
N/A
- Anonymous
Certificación como Organismo de Control Autorizado.
- Anonymous
No he participado en certificación

slido

6. Según tu experiencia, ¿qué barrera/s has encontrado durante la instalación de tecnologías de H2?

Multiple Choice Poll 12 votes 12 participants

slido

7 Annex 3: Fuelling tomorrow workshop

7.1 FLYER and AGENDA

Stazioni di rifornimento idrogeno; dalle pratiche europee alla situazione italiana

**10 ottobre 15.30 - Sala Blu (Pad 22)
FUELING TOMORROW - Bologna**

Attraverso gli investimenti del PNRR l'Italia si doterà di una rete di stazioni di rifornimento idrogeno, con un obiettivo di raggiungere un numero pari a 40 al 2026. In parallelo il regolamento AFIR pone agli stati membri obblighi vincolanti sul posizionamento delle stazioni idrogeno ogni 200 km sulle reti TenT e in ogni nodo urbano entro il 2030. Queste condizioni hanno portato all'avvio di progetti in questo ambito, ma tante sono ancora le incertezze perlopiù legate alla necessità di supporto finanziario e ai gap normativi. H2IT e il Progetto HyPOP tracceranno lo stato dell'arte italiano confrontando l'approccio nazionale con la visione e le progettualità individuate a livello europeo. L'obiettivo principale sarà quello di condividere informazioni utili alle aziende che vogliono sviluppare i progetti, ai cittadini che vogliono conoscere meglio la tecnologia e alle istituzioni che vanno sensibilizzate sulle attuali criticità, affinché superandole diventino motivo di accelerazione per raggiungere i target sull'infrastruttura e di decarbonizzazione posti a livello europeo.

MODERA: Cristina Maggi - H2IT

15.30 - 15.35	INTRODUZIONE H2IT - Cristina Maggi, H2IT
15.35 - 15.55	Progetto HYPOP - Sicurezza e Permitting: approcci e best practices per la mobilità e il residenziale in EU - Mattia Miglietta, Environment Park
15.55 - 16.10	Sicurezza dell'idrogeno dalla produzione all'erogazione Quadro normativo e approccio alla progettazione - Stephen McPhail, Kiwa
16.10 - 16.20	Presentazione del Position Paper H2IT HRS - Valeria Bona, H2IT
16.20 - 16.50	Esperienze delle aziende: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Luigi D'Onofrio - Edison Next; o Piero Lodi - TPER; o Alessio Cogliati - Linde o Alessandro Iannotta - Italiana Petroli
16.50 - 17.30	Tavola rotonda e Q&A con tutti i relatori

8 Annex 4: Belgium local stakeholders' engagement workshop

WORKSHOP TITLE	Workshop on safety certification and permitting for hydrogen infrastructures
EVENT DATE	24/01/2025
DURATION	3h
PLACE	Online
CO-ORGANISER (IF ANY)	/
TOPICS ADDRESSED (SLCA, WP2'S QUESTIONS AS PROVIDED, ETC..)	<p>The topics addressed were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of HyPOP and presentation of the main results concerning safety and permitting in EU. • Focus on permitting for HRS in Belgium, Netherlands, France and Germany • Share of expert experiences about permitting hydrogen infrastructure
SHORT DESCRIPTION (EACH SESSION, TYPE OF INTERACTION, TOPICS DISCUSSED)	<p>The first topic of the meeting was the presentation of the HyPOP Project, which aims to raise awareness and trust in hydrogen technologies, particularly for mobility and residential applications. One of the activities of this project is to better understand the safety regulations, permitting processes, and technical guidelines across different European countries. The goal is to highlight some barriers and find best practices to overcome these obstacles.</p> <p>The first results of the HyPOP project were presented by the leader of the project, Mattia Miglietta from Envipark.</p> <p>Then, cluster TWEED focused on the main results for Belgium and its neighbouring countries. An overview of the guideline that already exist was presented for these countries.</p> <p>After the presentations, the participants shared experiences and challenges in obtaining permits for hydrogen projects, emphasizing the need for clearer regulations and improved communication between stakeholders to facilitate the adoption of hydrogen technologies. Sertius also highlight the importance of considering water management and noise issues in the permitting process.</p> <p>The following improvement was proposed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include insurance companies among the stakeholders. Indeed, they are often forgotten even though they are essential for the well development of the project. If the insurance company does not find the project secure, it will not insure the project. • Need for specific files and the best available technologies for hydrogen production. • Permitting process in Wallonia is more subjective and lacks concrete practices, while Flanders has a more objective and

	<p>scientific approach. The stakeholders need a well-defined process for permitting hydrogen projects in the Walloon region.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for a change in the classifications in Wallonia for permitting procedures. For example, the Industrial Emission Directive (IED) should not be mandatory for hydrogen facilities (as is the case in Flanders). • Improve the experiences and the involvement of the Industrial Risk Departments (department of the Walloon administration). Indeed, it could result in shorter delays and better evaluation of the projects. • Reduce the delays in obtaining permits in Wallonia. Today, the permitting process can take up to a year or more. • Develop a unified EU-level guideline for hydrogen technology permitting • Improve social acceptance and trust in the safety of hydrogen projects. This is even more important than including additional security measures. <p>And the following actions for next 6 months:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize a follow-up meeting • Share results from similar HyPOP meetings in other countries (Italy, Spain, Poland and Bulgaria). • Share contact information for potential firefighter training opportunities. • Discuss with STIB (public buses in Brussels) for their experiences with hydrogen bus implementation. • Proposition of a guideline for Wallonia. • Include the Industrial Risk Departments in the discussion
<p>SPEAKERS (NAME, AFFILIATION)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Simon Habran - Cluster TWEED</i> ○ <i>Mattia Miglietta - Envi Park</i> ○ <i>Xavier Muschoot, Sertius - Company in environmental and safety services</i> ○ <i>Catherine Goormaghtigh, Colruyt Group - Food Store Chain</i> ○ <i>Sébastien Dubois, RESA - Gas and electricity distribution network</i> ○ <i>Patrick Hendrick, Université Libre de Bruxelles</i>
<p>INTERACTIVE QUESTIONS TO THE AUDIENCE (IF ANY) AND RESULTS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What are the main challenges you have encountered in obtaining or granting permits for hydrogen-related projects? Please describe your experience with environmental, safety, construction and/or administrative requirements and explain specific bottlenecks that you believe should be addressed. <p>Administrative requirements are unclear in Wallonia. Generally speaking, public services are fearful of this new technology. This is due to a lack of experience, as these people are generally unfamiliar with hydrogen. At Colruyt, for their permitting process in Wallonia, they</p>

invited Walloon authorities to their first HRS in Flanders to raise awareness of this technology.

=> Training and awareness-raising among authorities is essential, and it is primarily the industry that can participate in this process.

After obtaining a permit, you need to ensure your project, and this is also a delicate step, given that the insurance company must have confidence in the project so as not to charge exorbitant prices or require additional safety measures. So, we face the same problem: we need to raise awareness among stakeholders.

Need for a change in the classifications in Wallonia for permitting procedures. For example, the Industrial Emission Directive (IED) should not be mandatory for hydrogen facilities (as is the case in Flanders). Indeed, this directive is very restrictive.

- How does the environmental permitting process for hydrogen projects compare to that for other energy technologies? What improvement do you suggest?

The same problem arose during the development of compressed natural gas in stations. Colruyt Group had to meet with all the authorities and firefighters in each municipality to convince them that the installation would work and did not pose excessive risks. The problem, therefore, is not the technology, but the perception, the awareness of the public and stakeholders regarding new technologies. We can develop multiple safety measures and implement technologies that eliminate risks, but the major problem remains people's perception of this new technology.

- Have you experienced significant differences in permitting processes between regions or municipalities? If so, how do these disparities affect project implementation? Additionally, what improvements would you propose to harmonize or streamline these processes?

There's a problem with subjectivity in administrative monitoring in Wallonia. The administration will ask questions of competent people like the firefighters, but there's no clear framework to follow. The framework in Flanders is better defined and therefore more objective. In Flanders, there's a well-defined permitting process, but not in Wallonia. The administration has no expertise in the field of hydrogen, so it often refers to the SEVESO regulations, even for small projects. No specific acceptance criteria => they follow SEVESO criteria, which are very restrictive for HRS.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are the main challenges in demonstrating the safety of hydrogen plants <p>As already mentioned above, there is no technical challenge; the real challenge is the acceptance of the stakeholder to demonstrate it is safe.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What improvements would you propose to overcome regulatory barriers in your country? <p>Regulatory framework that is different for the different member state. Why there is not an EU regulatory framework/guidelines</p> <p>+ See survey outside the table</p>
NR OF ATTENDANCE	18
GENERAL INFO ABOUT THE AUDIENCE TYPE (e.g., x % of academia, x% of companies etc)	Essentially, companies, one university, one public entity (see the list of attendance)

Website link (video, presentation, ...):

<https://clusters.wallonie.be/tweed/home/actualites/actualites/feed-back-hypop-workshop-safety-certification-and-permitting-hydrogen-infrastructures.html>

Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0u54XHTLKZ8&t=1210s>

Slides: https://fr.slideshare.net/slideshow/feed-back-whatsapp-in-europe-regarding-h2-regulations-12-decembre-2024/274182179?_gl=1*sxdav5*_gcl_au*OTAxNzYyMTE1LjE3NTkxMzYzODI.

Survey:

1. What guidelines could Wallonia rely on regarding permitting?

The BAT of Flanders	2/6 (33%)
The PSG35 of the Netherlands	1/6 (17%)
A mix of BAT and PSG35	2/6 (33%)
We must create a new guideline	0/6 (0%)

2. If you choose "other", specify your answer here:

patrick.hendrick@ulb.ac.be

Something coherent with Flanders, but maybe not the BAT ...

Anonymous

Depending on the speed of work: speed PSG; if we can take more time the mix

3. For technical specifications like internal distances, is it better to:

Fix the specifications in a clear regulation	1/5 (20%)
The specifications are calculated and motivated by the operators => case by case approach.	3/5 (60%)
It depends on which specification	1/5 (20%)

4. If you choose "it depends" for which specifications a clear regulation is needed

patrick.hendrick@ulb.ac.be

ISO standards are existing ...

Anonymous

For standard gas stations (below a certain quantity of H₂), we should have specifications in a clear regulation, and risk analysis for bigger projects.

List of registered people:

First name	Name	Organisation	Present
Remy	Balegamire Baraka	Cluster TWEED	Oui
Cédric	Brüll	TWEED	Oui
ilaria	Schiavi	environment park spa	Oui
Katiuscia	Costabello	IRIS srl	Oui
ALBERTO	GARCIA	Clean Hydrogen Partnership	Oui
Nuno	Canha	HyLab - Green Hydrogen Collaborative Laboratory	Oui
Tatiana	Block	New Energy Coalition	Oui
Mark	Philips	SGS Belgium NV	Non
Thomas	Mergny	JANSON BAUGNIET	Oui
Marc	Marc Van Den Neste	District Cleantech	Oui
Lucie	Guerin	Sertius	Oui
thibaut	steenhuizen	Service public de Wallonie	Non
Xavier	Musschoot	Sertius	Oui
Emmanuel	Lheureux	Service Public de Wallonie - direction des risques industriels géologiques et miniers	Non
Catherine	Goormaghtigh	Colruyt Group	Oui
Patrick	Hendrick	ULB	Oui

Sébastien	Dubois	RESA	Oui
FRANCHINO	MARIANNA	ENVIRONMENT PARK	Oui
Laurent	Lognay	WE	Oui
Dirk	Vandercammen	Virya Energy	Oui
Simon	Habran	Cluster TWEED	Oui
Nathalie	Licops	TWEED	Non

9 Annex 5: Bulgaria local stakeholders' engagement workshop

The meeting on the HYPOP project was organized by the Balkan Hydrogen Cluster on 27/01/25 in Sofia.

The event was **attended** by:

1. Representative of the State Agency for Meteorology and Technical Supervision – Stoyan Stoyanov;
2. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences – Ivo Baev;
3. Thracian University – Ivan Milanov;
4. University of National and World Economy;
5. National Fire and Civil Safety Service;
6. Sofia University – Tsvetan Madanski;
7. Topolovgrad Municipality;
8. Shumen Municipality;
9. Chelopech Municipality
10. Balkan Hydrogen Cluster

The event took place according to the following **agenda**:

1. Balkan Hydrogen Cluster presented to the participants an explanation of the HYPOP project;
 2. The main legislative priorities of the EU countries on the topic of hydrogen were discussed;
 3. A discussion was organized on the topic of the safety of hydrogen use;
 4. The priorities for industry and transport in the production and use of green hydrogen were presented.
- 1 – Vasilimir Radulov presented the HYPOP project and introduced its participants. The participants in the event appreciated the benefits of the participation of a Bulgarian institution in such an international and strategic project;
- 2 – The representative of the State Meteorological Agency gave a full overview of the measures taken in Bulgaria and in the most legislatively advanced countries on the topic of hydrogen. The participants took the floor and expressed the opinion that state authorities should be proactive and

introduce legislative norms more quickly in order to enable business to introduce hydrogen on a mass scale;

3 – The National Fire Safety and Civil Protection Service introduced the participants to all legal and regulatory requirements and practical examples in the production, storage and use of hydrogen;

4 – Balkan Hydrogen Cluster and representatives of municipalities and universities introduced the participants to all perspectives and opportunities for the use of green hydrogen. Possibilities for creating Hydrogen Energy Communities on a local basis for the benefit of municipalities and businesses were discussed.

The topic **SAFETY**, related to hydrogen projects, was discussed by representatives of both the Meteorological Agency and the Fire Department, as well as by representatives of local authorities – the municipalities, on whose territory such projects are actually being or will be deployed. According to the laws and regulations of the Republic of Bulgaria – such types of projects involving hydrogen are implemented in accordance with the Law on Spatial Planning and the Regulation on the Storage and Transport of Gases under Pressure. These documents describe requirements such as pressure, distances, requirements if necessary for the premises, transportation and storage of hydrogen. This is how each such project is put into operation. There are no separate requirements for collecting and transmitting data from the projects, but each investor sets such a methodology to monitor and analyse data and processes. Currently, there is one separate hydrogen project on the territory of Bulgaria, and it has been put into operation under the laws described above – the modular charging station under the project of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. The Balkan Hydrogen Cluster is in a working group of the State Meteorological Agency, and is expected to soon launch a process on separate norms and requirements for hydrogen projects, with the aim of more widespread use of hydrogen. The first proposals for such norms and documents are expected to be released this year.

The topic of issuing **PERMITS** for hydrogen projects and the use of hydrogen was also touched upon by all participants.

Permits for the production and use of hydrogen are currently issued in Bulgaria by the State Meteorological Agency. It is planned to establish a working expert group within the Agency specifically for permits for hydrogen projects. The Chief Chemical Engineer of the Balkan Hydrogen Cluster – Stoyan Sabev will be the leader of this expert group, as he is currently one of the few experts with nearly 40 years of experience in the topic of hydrogen – having designed, built and exported various projects related to the production, use, storage and transport of hydrogen. Participants shared that they hope this group will give positive momentum to hydrogen projects and their permits.

CERTIFICATION

Currently, there is no certification provision for hydrogen-related projects and equipment in Bulgaria. In practice, both the Meteorological Agency and the Fire Service have made it clear that any hydrogen-related product is required to meet ISO safety standards, have a CE certificate and all other general requirements, but there is no separate regulatory framework for certification. This is set to be achieved by expanding the scope and number of hydrogen projects. At present, it is expected that a pilot certification project will be launched in cooperation between the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences and the Balkan Hydrogen Cluster, after coordination with the State Meteorological Agency.

10 Annex 6: Spain local stakeholders' engagement workshop

WORKSHOP TITLE	"Proyecto HYPOP: Abordando las barreras en el sector del hidrógeno" (HYPOP project: Tackling barriers in the hydrogen sector)
EVENT DATE	6 th February 2025
DURATION	09:00 – 9:45 (45 min)
PLACE	CONGRESO NACIONAL DE HIDRÓGENO VERDE (NATIONAL GREEN HYDROGEN CONGRESS) Casa Colón Conference Centre Huelva (Spain)
CO-ORGANISER (IF ANY)	CONGRESO NACIONAL DE HIDRÓGENO VERDE
TOPICS ADDRESSED (SLCA, WP2'S QUESTIONS AS PROVIDED ETC..)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - INTRODUCTION TO HYPOP PROJECT - S-LCA - PERMITTING, SECURITY AND CERTIFICATION REQUIREMENTS - WP2 QUESTIONS - INTERACTION WITH THE AUDIENCE
SHORT DESCRIPTION (EACH SESSION, TYPE OF INTERACTION, TOPICS DISCUSSED)	<p>INTRODUCTION TO HYPOP PROJECT AND TO THE WORKSHOP</p> <p>First of all, the speakers (María and Gema) were introduced by the Congress presenter. A short introduction about CNH2 was carried out, followed by an explanation of the session dynamic.</p> <p>Since it was an interactive session, the assistants were shown a QR code to access to a Google Form so they could answer the different questions raised during the presentation. The different parts of the survey (data protection, personal data and interactive questions) were explained to the audience. The first question (1) was launched to know the profile of the attendants.</p> <p>Having this done, HYPOP project (objectives, scope, consortium and phases) was presented to the audience.</p> <p>PERMITTING, SECURITY AND CERTIFICATION REQUIREMENTS</p> <p>As the session evolved, the analysis of the stakeholder's requirements was presented. The question n°2 was raised so as to know if the audience was more related with the permitting,</p>

security or certification phase. An open section (“Other: ...”) was added to the survey for those cases in which none of the options were applicable.

The results obtained in WP2 were presented, distinguishing the three main topics addressed: permitting, security and certification. The focus was put in the Spanish regulations and requirements, but some highlights were given about the other European countries analysed to emphasize the huge contrast among countries.

Questions nº 3, 4 and 5 were merged with the slides of this part, with the aim of combining the results presented with the participation of the audience.

END OF THE PRESENTATION AND PROMOTION OF THE HYPOP COMMUNITY

Having presented the stakeholders requirements, the last question (6) was launched to conclude the interactive questions. This question was formulated with the aim of summarizing all the content of the presentation and to know the main barriers faced by the audience in their respective projects and experiences.

A few minutes were given to the assistants for finalising the survey and the “Join our community” card was exposed to show the social media and the webpage of the project.

REVIEW OF THE SURVEY RESULTS AND OPEN DEBATE

Once the presentation was finalised, the speakers commented the results obtained for every of the interactive questions in the survey (33 responses), connecting them with the different experiences encountered along the project.

In the time left, a microphone was given to the audience so they could publicly share their opinions, views and experiences.

The first participant from the public complained about a lack of coordination among the different authorities: national ministries, regional committees (for example, *Junta de Andalucía*) and local governments... Even in a “same-level” government, sometimes there are discrepancies between different departments (Industry, Environment, etc.).

Apart from that, when it comes to certification, the difficulty of finding a certifying body (someone doing the certification of a hydrogen infrastructure) was raised.

As a consequence, it was also highlighted the importance of proper training for authorities and certification bodies.

Another attendant had interest in the phase of analysis of HYPOP project, and asked if the yet-existing procedures, authorities, stakeholders, etc. for the chemical industry had been or would be taken into account when addressing the permitting, security or certification phase of a hydrogen facility. The speakers answered affirmatively and gave some examples.

To conclude, one of the organisers of the event emphasized the importance of unifying the different points of view and disseminating the advances in the hydrogen sector. He also underlined the relevant role of HYPOP project in these tasks.

<p>SPEAKERS (NAME, AFFILIATION)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gema Rodado (CNH2) María Panadero (CNH2) 																														
<p>INTERACTIVE QUESTIONS TO THE AUDIENCE (IF ANY) AND RESULTS</p>	<p>1. In which part of the hydrogen value chain do you work?</p> <p>Multiple choice was allowed, so some people answered more than one option. The table shows how many of the 33 respondents marked each item in number and percentage.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Options given</th> <th>N°</th> <th>%</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Electrolysis</td> <td>7</td> <td>21</td> </tr> <tr> <td>H2 production (alternative to electrolysis)</td> <td>4</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Generating sets (gensets)</td> <td>2</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Fuel cells</td> <td>5</td> <td>15</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Storage of liquids / gases / solids</td> <td>8</td> <td>24</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hydrogen cylinders/cylinder packs/pressurised tanks for road transport (as hazardous substance)</td> <td>4</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Hydrogen gas compressors</td> <td>4</td> <td>12</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Regulation and permitting</td> <td>10</td> <td>30</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other</td> <td>17</td> <td>52</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>For the 17 people who selected the option “Other”, the answers added were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Related with H2 projects: “H2 Project Management”, “Renewable energy and hydrogen promoter” (as a complement to Electrolysis), “Interregional collaborations”, “The entire value chain” (4) Related with equipment and deployments: “Instrumentation”, “Construction”, “Electrical material and instrumentation distributor”, “Process engineering development”, “Project engineering”, “Technology integration” (as a complement to Regulation and permitting). (6) Related with firefighters and security authorities: “Emergency services” (1) Related with research: “Research and development”, “Research in hydrogen technology” (2) Others: “Port”, “Training”, “I don’t work”, “Consumer” (4) <p>2. Thinking about the national projects in which you have participated, in which phase have you been more involved?</p>	Options given	N°	%	Electrolysis	7	21	H2 production (alternative to electrolysis)	4	12	Generating sets (gensets)	2	6	Fuel cells	5	15	Storage of liquids / gases / solids	8	24	Hydrogen cylinders/cylinder packs/pressurised tanks for road transport (as hazardous substance)	4	12	Hydrogen gas compressors	4	12	Regulation and permitting	10	30	Other	17	52
Options given	N°	%																													
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Only one answer was allowed. Those who marked the option “Others” wrote the following answers:

- **Related with equipment and deployments:** Site, manufacturing, reception (this person answered “Storage of liquids / gases / solids” in question 1), maintenance.
- **Related with engineering:** Conceptual and basic engineering, design, selection of the right materials.
- **Related with management:** Strategy, management and coordination, interregional collaborations, legal structuring of projects.
- **Related with research:** R&D (2 people)
- **Related with education:** Training and technical regulations, training

3. Thinking about the H2 projects that you know; would you be able to say which are the relevant authorities for granting the Implementation or commissioning of this project?

This question was open so people could add the authorities considered in case of an affirmative answer.

- 26 people (79%) answered “Yes” or directly commented some authorities.
- 5 people (15%) answered “No”.
- 2 people (6%) wrote a different answer: “50/50” and “No todas” (Not all).

The authorities mentioned, from most to least were:

- Regional Government
- City Council (Local Government)
- Regional Industry Department (Regional Government)
- Ministry of Industry, Energy (National Government)
- Regional Environmental Department (Regional Government)
- Hydrological Confederation
- Ministry (National Government)
- Regional Authority
- Spanish Electricity Grid (REE)
- Ministry of Development (National Government)

- Local/regional/national administrations, depending on whether or not powers have been transferred
- Official State Gazette (*BOE, Boletín Oficial del Estado*)
- Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (National Government)

4. Which are the main challenges for demonstrating security in hydrogen technologies?

While 2 people answered “I do not know”, the other 31 participated with different comments about:

- **Knowledge:** the general lack of information or awareness and the lack of definition.
- **Public opinion:** credibility, social awareness (fighting false myths, raising awareness in society that H2 has been with us for decades) and social issues.
- **Regulation and certification:** lack of specific regulation, lack of a unique specific regulation, certification, standardized best practices, homogeneity.
- **Environmental prevention.**
- **Techno-economic issues:** costs, economic issues, demand, use of the technology, machinery operating hours, anticipation of storage equipment degradation, facility design, storage, distribution, making H2 closer to people through HRS.
- **Security:** security in general, explosive zones, H2 flammability, pressure in H2 generation and storage, lack of previous accident data (for validating safety level). Developing, disseminating and applying passive and active security measures.

5. (a) Do you have experience in H2 technologies certification?

Only one answer was allowed:

5. (b) Do you know any guideline or protocol for certification?

The regulations mentioned where:

- **CertifHy:** initiative started in 2014 and financed by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership with the objective of taking Europe-wide green and low carbon hydrogen certification to the next level: from concept to implementation
- **ISO standard 14687-2:2012:** "Hydrogen fuel – Product specification".
- **SAE J2719 standard:** "Hydrogen Fuel Quality for Fuel Cell Vehicles".
- **ISO standard 19880-1:2020:** "Gaseous hydrogen – Fuelling stations".

6. What barrier/s have you encountered during the installation of H2 technologies?

9 people answered "do not know", "no answer" or something similar; one person said that they had no installed (any H2 technology) still and other said that they had not found barriers so far.

The rest of the answers (22 people) can be grouped in 4 categories:

- **Economic viability:** Some barriers as "funding", "competitiveness without grant", "offer-demand balance/lack of off-takers", "costs rationalization" were raised.
- **Knowledge:** lack of information and awareness (in general and on the part of the administrations), availability of previous infrastructures and lack of precedents were also shown as a problem.
- **Security:** ignorance about security, security itself and difficulty in detecting hydrogen leakages were other topics addressed.
- **Permitting and certification:** around 11 people complained about the lack of regulation, regulatory ambiguity/interpretative discrepancies/different criteria between different entities of the same government, fear of risk, lack of a single certification and permitting body, products to be included in the certification process, delivery and execution deadlines and permitting and certification in general.

7. Anything else to add?

Two people used this space to add an additional comment to the questions answered. One of them highlighted the importance of disseminating the H2 properties and the security measures applied in H2 usage, such as detection. The other one was worried about H2 implementation, saying that there are many projects on paper but few projects in actual execution, and that the green hydrogen price (€/kg) is not well defined.

<p>NR OF ATTENDANCE</p>	<p>>50 (33 answers to the interactive questions)</p>
<p>GENERAL INFO ABOUT THE AUDIENCE TYPE (e.g. x % of academia, x% of companies etc)</p>	<p>Among the public there was representation from different types of stakeholders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 authorities from Port Authority of Huelva and Andalusian Energy Agency (regional government) • 1 person from Emergency Services/ Fire Services Company (FALCK) • 17 people from private energetic/engineering companies: Enagás, HUNOSA Group, Oinse, COLLOSA, Moeve, Orbita ingeniería, Clantech, Elektra Andalucía XXI, Planea Hidrógeno, Idea Energía, Realza Ingenieros, Marwen Calsan group, CMC Cerezuela, Hidroever, Acerinox. • 1 person from Sedigas (The Spanish Gas Association, non-profit association). • 1 person from TÜV SÜD. • 1 independent worker. • 4 people from public entities: City of Energy foundation (attached to the Institute for Just Transition (ITJ) of the Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO)), CNH2 and INTA (National Institute of Aerospace Technology). • 2 people from hydrogen associations (H2CYL, Costa Rican Hydrogen Association) • 3 people from the education sector (Vocational training teacher, student, researcher from University of Huelva)

Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GphtPTVev0E>

Linkedin post from the conference:
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7296100239579529216/>

Photos:

Agenda:

https://congresohipopverde.com/?page_id=1142

Auditorio
moeve

Martes 4 Miércoles 5 Jueves 6

Jueves, 6 de Febrero 2025

Mesa 9 9:00h - 9:45h

PROYECTO HYPOP: HYDROGEN PUBLIC OPINION AND ACCEPTANCE

Ponentes

- Gema María Rodado Nieto, jefa de la Unidad de Consultoría y Formación del Centro Nacional del Hidrógeno
- María Panadero Camacho, técnico de la Unidad de Consultoría y Formación del Centro Nacional del Hidrógeno

Mesa 10 9:45h - 10:30h

CONTENIDO DE LA FORMACIÓN PROFESIONAL PARA LA INDUSTRIA DEL H2V

Moderador
Narciso Rojas, responsable de Comunicación en Moeve y Fundación Moeve en Huelva

Ponentes

- Manuel Contreras Acuña, profesor del CPIFP Profesor José Luis Graño, coordinador dual grupo HV Química Industrial y Coordinador del grupo de trabajo "Adecuación curricular de la FP a las nuevas tecnologías del hidrógeno verde" (CEP Bollullos Valverde)
- Florentino Santos Porras, secretario general de Formación Profesional de la Consejería de Desarrollo Educativo y Formación Profesional
- Guillermo Figueruelo Malo, responsable de Estrategia en Fundación de Hidrógeno de Aragón
- Victoria Martín-Lomeña Guerrero, secretaria general del Servicio Público de Empleo y Formación
- Rafael Fernández Qundez, director de talento de Moeve

9:00 – 9:10: Introduction and HYPOP project presentation.

9:10 – 9:25: Main results of the project.

9:25 – 9:45: Debate with the audience.

(Interactive questions have been carried out during the HYPOP project and the main results presentation)

11 Annex 7: Poland local stakeholders' engagement workshop

Title of the meeting: Development of the Hydrogen Economy in the Pomeranian Region

Date: 15 May 2025
Location: Marshal's Office of the Pomeranian Voivodeship, Gdansk
Participants: 18 representatives of key regional stakeholders

1. Objective of the Meeting

The meeting aimed to introduce the HYPOP project (Hydrogen Public Opinion and Acceptance) and to initiate an in-depth, constructive interregional discussion on the potential and challenges related to the hydrogen economy. Financed by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership, HYPOP addresses the issue of building social trust in hydrogen technologies, especially in public transport and housing. The session highlighted project partnerships, planned outcomes, and community engagement methodologies. Participants were familiarized with HYPOP's importance in both European and regional hydrogen strategies.

2. Meeting Agenda and Presentation of HYPOP

The meeting opened with a presentation of the HYPOP project's goals and structure. The project's territorial scope and international consortium—comprising hydrogen clusters, research institutes, and public communication organizations—were introduced. A particular focus was given to the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) methodology, used to identify social hotspots in hydrogen projects. Best practices in certification and safety developed at the EU level were also presented. Implementation tools were discussed, including:

- The multimedia HYPOP platform featuring videos, analyses, and public opinion survey results,
- A set of indicators to assess the social impact of hydrogen technology deployment.

Participants gained a comprehensive overview of the tools and mechanisms HYPOP employs to support social acceptance of hydrogen technologies.

3. Participants

The meeting gathered representatives from various sectors—industry, public administration, and environmental expertise. This cross-sectoral presence ensured a holistic view of hydrogen economy development.

Represented institutions included:

- Port of Gdansk – transport and logistics infrastructure
- Gaz-System – gas system operator
- ASE Group – provider of energy and technology solutions
- SES Hydrogen – hydrogen sector company
- Eko-Konsult – environmental consultancy
- Marshal's Office of the Pomeranian Voivodeship – regional government authority

The composition of participants allowed for a comprehensive discussion from the perspectives of investors, regulators, and local communities.

4. Key Discussion Topics

During the discussion session, participants shared experiences, needs, and challenges related to hydrogen project implementation. The following key issues were identified:

- Complexity and lack of transparency in administrative procedures; lack of uniform local standards,
- Insufficient administrative competence in technical and legal aspects of hydrogen installations,
- Absence of coherent public communication tools and citizen engagement mechanisms,
- Untapped potential for synergy with EU-funded projects,
- The need for unified guidelines for the Pomeranian region.

The debate revealed both systemic and organizational barriers, but also pointed to actionable intervention areas for the short term.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the meeting's content, presentations, and discussions, a comprehensive list of conclusions and recommendations was developed. These should guide future regional actions for advancing the hydrogen economy in the Pomeranian Voivodeship:

- **Updating the Regional Strategy:** There is an urgent need to revise the Pomeranian regional development strategy to include a social component reflecting citizens' attitudes, knowledge, and readiness to accept new technologies. This includes defining regional indicators for social acceptance and establishing monitoring mechanisms for public engagement in planning and implementation. Strategic alignment with EU documents such as REPowerEU and the Hydrogen Strategy for a Climate-Neutral Europe is advised.
- **Improving Local Government Capacity:** Gaps in public administration knowledge—particularly regarding the interpretation of technical standards, environmental impact assessments, HSE regulations, and certification procedures—were identified. A modular training programme is recommended, covering legal, technical, and social aspects. An accessible knowledge base, such as an e-learning platform linked to HYPOP, should be developed.
- **Adapting HYPOP Tools Locally:** HYPOP tools—such as the communication platform, public engagement models, S-LCA indicators, and EU-level best practices—can and should be localized. Their application would support decision-making, improve investor transparency, and strengthen community trust.
- **Strengthening Education and Public Communication:** There is a pressing need to increase public outreach and educational efforts. Suggested actions include local media campaigns, community debates, information meetings, and integration of hydrogen topics into secondary and vocational school curricula. A citizen's guide on hydrogen technologies could serve as part of HYPOP's public dissemination materials.
- **Integration with National and EU Projects:** The region should actively participate in EU hydrogen development programmes (e.g., CertifHy). It is recommended to establish a coordination unit to facilitate applications for international research and implementation projects, which would boost funding access and technology transfer.

- **Developing Regional Roadmaps and Implementation Scenarios:** Participatory and realistic hydrogen technology development roadmaps are needed for key sectors—transport, heating, energy-intensive industries, and housing. These should involve local communities, experts, and investors to avoid conflict and foster co-ownership of technological progress.

These recommendations form a coherent framework for building a socially accepted, safe, and sustainable hydrogen economy in the Pomeranian region. Their successful implementation requires active involvement from administration, private sector, research institutions, and citizens—leveraging HYPOP as a tool and catalyst for regional action.

6. Next Steps

To follow up on the meeting, the following actions were proposed:

- Organizing regional workshops with local community participation,
- Formally including the Pomeranian Voivodeship in the group of regions piloting HYPOP guidelines,
- Reflecting the discussed issues in the update of the regional energy and climate strategy and in the programming documents under the FEnIKS 2021–2027 initiative.

These planned activities aim to strengthen the region's role in the European energy transition and harness social potential for implementing hydrogen innovations.

12 Annex 8: Italy local stakeholders' engagement workshop

WORKSHOP TITLE	NORMATIVE E PROGETTI IN EVOLUZIONE: dialogo tra operatori e autorità della filiera dell'idrogeno sulla sicurezza, le procedure e il coinvolgimento della società civile
EVENT DATE	23 rd of May 2025
DURATION	10:30 – 12:30 CEST
PLACE	Hydrogen Expo Piacenza
CO-ORGANISER (IF ANY)	H2IT – Italian Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Association
TOPICS ADDRESSED (SLCA, WP2'S QUESTIONS AS PROVIDED ETC..)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safety requirements and barriers - Permitting requirements and barriers - Main technologies suffering certification gaps - Importance of guidelines for safety and permitting - Relevance of risk assessment and identification of the best methodologies <p>To understand perception of the audience about safety, permitting, and certification, check the answers from Slido Q&A reported below.</p>
SHORT DESCRIPTION (EACH SESSION, TYPE OF INTERACTION, TOPICS DISCUSSED)	<p>MAIN OUTPUTS FROM SAFETY & CERTIFICATION SESSION (a likely safety authority engagement discussion):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project introduction (Safety): Present the project to the fire brigade command, making it easier to understand and accelerating the approval process. • Normative references: Review with the fire brigades which ministerial decrees and regulations apply to each section of the installation. • Critical issues: Analyse potential project criticalities and identify suitable mitigation measures. • Needs: Implement existing safety regulations, introducing specific conditions for each possible project size and technologies installed • Tools: To require risk assessment and to specify which methodology is desired • Approach: To reason on the likely of incident scenarios instead of gravity

	<p>MAIN OUTPUT FOR PERMITTING:</p> <p>Project introduction (Permitting): Essential to present the project in advance to the authorities and administrations in order to gather comments/suggestions and then develop a design for “fit for purpose” permits.</p> <p>See description below for details.</p>
SPEAKERS (NAME, AFFILIATION)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrico Villa Hydrogen project developer company (SIMPLIFHY) • Diomede Malvaso Certification company (RINA) • Gabriele Ballocco Fire safety company (RAMS&E srl) • Francesco Bonadeo TSO company (SNAM) • Francesca De Falco Public authority for environmental permitting (REGIONE CAMPANIA) • Francesco Vitali Engineering company for environmental permitting (TECHFEM)
INTERACTIVE QUESTIONS TO THE AUDIENCE (IF ANY) AND RESULTS	(see results from Q&A Slido sessions)
NR OF ATTENDANCE	Up to 45 participants (in presence)
GENERAL INFO ABOUT THE AUDIENCE TYPE (e.g. x % of academia, x% of companies etc)	Private companies and public authorities

SAFETY AND CERTIFICATION SESSION

The first speaker was **Simplifhy**, an Italian company specialising in hydrogen projects, which shared its experience and the main criticalities it has encountered. They stressed how hard it is to bring the many different kinds of hydrogen-distribution plants—both in terms of scale and technology—under the technical fire-safety rule that currently addresses only hydrogen-production plants.

Specifically:

- **Ministerial Decree (MD) 7 July 2023** does not tailor its requirements to the size of the plant (problem of applicability).
- Safer technologies, such as **metal-hydride storage** are **not mentioned** in the national fire-safety regulations (technology gap).

- Some plants fall under **both** relevant MDs, yet those decrees impose **different requirements on the same components** (regulatory ambiguity).

Key regulatory differences

Buffer (pressure-damping) vessels

- **MD 23 Oct 2018**
 - The geometric volume of pressure-damping vessels must **not exceed 0.4 m³**.
- **MD 7 Jul 2023**
 - For vessels damping pulsations above **150 bar(g)** the geometric volume must **not exceed 0.4 m³**.
 - Where the volume **exceeds 0.4 m³**, a **specific risk assessment** is required.

Fire-protection requirements

- **MD 23 Oct 2018**
 - Skids of tube-trailers and any storage unit made up of two or more unshielded cylinders with a capacity > **1500 Nm³** must be protected by an **automatic-plus-manual water-spray cooling system** (subject to the limits in § 2.5).
- **MD 7 Jul 2023**
 - **All compressed-hydrogen storage**—except cylinder bundles with a geometric volume < **1 m³**—must also be protected by **water-spray cooling systems**.

These mismatches make it difficult for project developers to ensure compliance and highlight the need for a harmonised, technology-neutral regulatory framework.

Moreover, the safety requirements for the distribution plants discussed by the company are extremely stringent:

1. Protective walls

- Non-combustible, mechanically robust enclosures must be built around every hazardous component.

2. Safety distances

- Both **internal** distances (between plant components) and **external** distances (between the plant and surrounding buildings) must be observed.

3. Fire-protection systems

- Mandatory installation of a hydrant network, sprinkler systems, and fire-detection devices to safeguard all hazardous equipment.

Reference technical standards

- **UNI CEN/TS 14816 – Water-spray systems: design, installation and maintenance**
 - Requires a discharge density > 10 mm min^{-1} .
- **UNI 10779 – Fire-extinguishing systems, hydrant networks: design, installation and operation**
 - Requires a water flow of 300 L min^{-1} for **four hydrants**.
- **UNI EN 12845 – Fixed firefighting systems, automatic sprinkler systems**
 - Provides guidance on system design, risk classification, installation, inspection and maintenance.

The second speaker shared his vision towards the actual public perception towards hydrogen projects. In particular, RAMS&E shared its perspective, **emphasizing risk analysis as a tool for demonstrating the safety of a hydrogen plant to the fire-brigade authorities**. They suggest providing more detail on which risk-assessment methodologies are required to meet prescriptive regulations. There is also a common view that a fully quantitative risk assessment is excessive for the majority of hydrogen applications and projects. **The new fire-safety rules specific to hydrogen-production projects call for a risk analysis only for the production system, but not for the other plant components.**

The audience confirmed the need to further disseminate knowledge about the real risks of hydrogen among public authorities, such as fire-brigade commands. **RINA, the certification body, also reported that a discussion table has been opened with the ministry on the need to introduce the role of a fire-safety designer—an expert who can certify the safety of a project in support of the public authorities.** Risk perception is still distorted by the scenario that, while described in analyses as the most severe, is actually the least likely.

PERMITTING SESSION

Permitting drew considerable interest from the audience, sparking a lively debate on several features of the current regulatory framework. SNAM shared the example of a hydrogen-valley project that successfully made it through the authorisation process. The project centres on a 2.5 MW electrolyser powered by a 6 MW photovoltaic plant and includes four loading bays for tube-trailer filling.

Permitting pathway

Step	Legal reference	Competent authority	Permit scope
Exemption from Environmental-Impact Assessment (EIA) and from EIA Screening	Italian Env. Code, Leg. Decree 152/2006 – Art. 6-bis, Annex II, Part II; Art. 8 (I), Annex IV, Part II	–	Environmental
Derogation from Integrated Environmental Authorisation (AIA)	Leg. Decree 152/2006 – Art. 4.2.a, Annex VIII, Part II	Emilia-Romagna Region	Environmental
Single Authorisation (Autorizzazione Unica) under Art. 12 DPR 380/2003, issued pursuant to Leg. Decree 199/2021	–	ARPAE SAC Modena	Urban-planning/building
Project assessment under Fire-Safety Regulations	DPR 151/2011 – Art. 3 (activities 1.1.C, 2.2.C, 3.3.C, 49.1.A)	Provincial Fire Brigade Command, Modena	Safety/fire
Single Environmental Authorisation (AUA)	–	–	Discharges, emissions, etc.
Permit to discharge water into a watercourse and sewer	–	–	Environmental
No-objection from the Superintendency of Archaeology, Fine Arts and Landscape	–	–	Cultural-heritage & landscape
Declaration of no interference with ENAV (air-navigation services)	–	–	Aviation

One of the main criticalities added by low experience and perception of public authorities towards hydrogen: although pursuant to Legislative Decree 199/2021, the size of the electrolysis unit would have allowed for free construction or at least PAS procedure, but as a precautionary measure, the Municipality of Modena requested the possibility of voluntarily proceeding with a Single Authorisation **resulting in a longer procedure.**

The new national environmental rules have cleared up previous interpretative doubts: green-hydrogen production projects are now explicitly exempt from an Environmental Impact Assessment when they involve refuelling stations or when the hydrogen is produced for downstream end uses. In addition, a derogation from EU legislation is expected that would remove this type of plant from the list of installations required to obtain an Integrated Environmental Authorisation.

Similarly, **Techfem** outlined its own permitting strategy for a hydrogen-production plant comparable to the one described earlier. The company filed a single digital application through the **ZES Calabria One-Stop Shop** on **30 November 2023**, bundling the following procedures:

Procedure	Description
Autorizzazione Integrata Ambientale (AIA) Regionale	Regional Integrated Environmental Authorisation
Autorizzazione Paesaggistica Ordinaria (interventions in areas subject to landscape restrictions, Art. 146, Leg. Decree 42/2004)	Ordinary Landscape Authorisation
Screening Valutazione d'Incidenza (VIncA)	Screening for Appropriate Assessment (Habitats Directive)
Valutazione Preventiva dell'Interesse Archeologico (VPIA)	Preliminary Archaeological Interest Assessment
Valutazione Previsionale di Impatto Acustico (Art. 8, Law 447/1995)	Forecast Noise-Impact Assessment
Dichiarazione Inizio Lavori Asseverata (DILA/CILA) for the photovoltaic plant	Self-Certified Start-of-Works Declaration for the PV array
Verifica di Compatibilità Idraulica - AdB Distretto Appennino Meridionale	Hydraulic-compatibility check by the Southern Apennines River Basin Authority
Istanza di Valutazione Progetto to the Catanzaro Fire Brigade (DPR 151/2011)	Project Evaluation Request to the Catanzaro Fire Brigade Command (fire-safety authorisation)
Valutazione Ostacoli ENAC/ENAV	Obstacle-clearance assessment by the Italian Civil Aviation Authority (ENAC) / Air-Navigation Service Provider (ENAV)

The following is the Agenda shown at the beginning of the national workshop describing the two main sessions of the event. Each session started with a presentation from Envipark regarding the objectives of HYPOP and with the results of WP2 technical analysis and the first outcomes from previous national workshops and international workshop.

AGENDA

<p>APPROCCI ALLA SICUREZZA E CERTIFICAZIONE DELLE TECNOLOGIE H2: GLI ESPERTI A CONFRONTO</p>	<p>PROCEDURE AUTORIZZATIVE H₂: SFIDE E OPPORTUNITÀ</p>
<p>10:30 - 10:50 HYPOP: Panoramica sulla Sicurezza, confronti internazionali e buone pratiche Mattia Miglietta, Environment Park</p>	<p>11:30 - 11:40 HYPOP: Panoramica sul Permitting confronti internazionali e buone pratiche Mattia Miglietta, Environment Park</p>
<p>10:50 - 11:30 Tavola rotonda "Sicurezza e Certificazione in Italia: barriere e possibili sviluppi" Relatori: Enrico Villa SIMPLIFHY Diomede Malvaso RINA Gabriele Ballocco RAMS&E</p>	<p>11:40 - 12:20 Tavola rotonda "Percorsi autorizzativi per l'idrogeno: barriere e sviluppi futuri" Relatori: Francesco Bonadeo SNAM Francesca De Falco REGIONE CAMPANIA Francesco Vitali TECHFEM</p>
<p>12:20 - 12:30 Conclusioni e survey finale</p>	

TAVOLA ROTONDA:

Sicurezza e Certificazione in Italia: barriere e possibili sviluppi

Enrico Villa | **SIMPLIFHY**
 Diomede Malvaso | **RINA**
 Gabriele Ballocco | **RAMS&E**

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TAVOLA ROTONDA:
Percorsi autorizzativi per l'idrogeno: barriere e sviluppi futuri

Francesco Bonadeo | SNAM
Processi autorizzativi di una Hydrogen Valley

Francesca De Falco | REGIONE CAMPANIA
La visione di Regione Campania nei processi autorizzativi

Francesco Vitali | TECHFEM
L'esperienza di Techfem nel permitting degli impianti idrogeno

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Each round table was characterized by a set of questions shared with the audience through Slido platform, allowing a dynamic Q&A between the speakers and the audience. The key takeaways have been collected and described here:

For safety:

- Limited training and awareness of the specific risks of hydrogen among local authorities
- New technical fire safety rules for hydrogen installations or amendments to existing rules with greater clarity and distinction between the different possible applications

For certification:

- Gaps in standards or certification processes, mainly concerning hydrogen refuelling stations

For permitting:

- Uncertainty in framing regulatory requirements with respect to the characteristics of hydrogen, its technologies and the project in general are the main difficulties
- The main gaps in permitting procedures concern safety permits

SAFETY AND CERTIFICATION – Q&A SESSION

H2EXPO - Sicurezza

Engaged participants 28 out of 45 Slido participants engaged with polls or Q&A. <div style="text-align: right;">62%</div>	Q&A engagement Your Q&A received no questions. <div style="text-align: center;">No data</div>	Poll engagement 28 out of 45 Slido participants voted in a poll. <div style="text-align: right;">62%</div>
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[Show more](#) ▾

Poll Insights

Quali sono le principali sfide nel dimostrare la sicurezza di progetti idrogeno, sia come soggetto che interagisce con le autorità, sia come autorità che valuta i progetti?

Quali sono le principali sfide nel dimostrare la sicurezza di progetti idrogeno, sia come soggetto che interagisce con le autorità, sia come autorità che valuta i progetti? Share ▾

Multiple Choice Poll 13 votes 13 participants

Mancanza di standard tecnici armonizzati e riconosciuti a livello nazionale - 2 votes	15%
Mancanza di scenari di riferimento per la valutazione dei rischi - 3 votes	23%
Limitata formazione e consapevolezza dei rischi specifici dell'idrogeno tra le autorità locali - 5 votes	38%
Eccessivo affidamento su parametri di sicurezza derivati da tecnologie convenzionali e approcci prescrittivi - 3 votes	23%
Altro - 0 votes	0%

Quali miglioramenti proporresti per superare le barriere normative per la sicurezza nel tuo Paese?

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Multiple Choice Poll 12 votes 12 participants

Creare uno sportello dedicato a livello nazionale o regionale con competenze tecniche e amministrative - 1 vote	8%
Promuovere la mutua diffusione di buone pratiche e di analisi del rischio tra Stati membri UE - 2 votes	17%
Nuove regole tecniche antincendio o modifiche a quelle esistenti con maggiore chiarezza e distinzione delle diverse applicazioni possibili - 7 votes	58%
Sviluppare programmi di formazione specifici per le autorità pubbliche sui rischi dell'idrogeno - 2 votes	17%
Altro - 0 votes	0%

Quali tecnologie sono più influenzate da lacune negli standard o nei processi di certificazione? (indicare una sola risposta)

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Poll Insights

Quali sono le principali sfide nel dimostrare la sicurezza di progetti idrogeno, sia come soggetto che interagisce con le autorità, sia come autorità che valuta i progetti?

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Multiple Choice Poll 18 votes 18 participants

Le stazioni di rifornimento a idrogeno (HRS) - 11 votes

Elettrolizzatori - 0 votes

Sistemi di stoccaggio - 3 votes

Fuel cell as CHP (micro-cogenerazione) che usano idrogeno puro o miscele - 0 votes

Altro - 4 votes

PERMITTING- Q&A SESSION

Poll Insights

Quali sono le principali difficoltà che hai riscontrato nell'ottenere o concedere permessi per progetti a idrogeno?

Quali sono i riferimenti normativi che presentano le maggiori lacune? (indicare una sola risposta)

Quali sono le principali difficoltà che hai riscontrato nell'ottenere o concedere permessi per progetti a idrogeno?

Multiple Choice Poll 6 votes 6 participants

Incertezza nell'inquadrare i requisiti normativi rispetto alle caratteristiche dell'idrogeno, delle sue tecnologie e del progetto in generale - 4 votes

Ritardi procedurali e mancanza di coordinamento tra le tempistiche per i diversi permessi (e.g., ambientali, sicurezza, urbanistici ...) per via della novità del vettore e della percezione pubblica - 1 vote

Carico documentale eccessivo per progetti idrogeno associati a contesti industriali o ad altri gas/vettori - 0 votes

Differenze tra processi autorizzativi a livello nazionale e regionale - 1 vote

Altro - 0 votes

Poll Insights

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Share

Multiple Choice Poll 4 votes 4 participants

Autorizzazioni e vincoli ambientali - 0 votes

Autorizzazioni e i vincoli per la sicurezza (es. antincendio) - 4 votes

Autorizzazioni e vincoli urbanistici. - 0 votes

Altro - 0 votes

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Let's make
the hydrogen
revolution

